

Research Article

Adventure Awaits: MyBACKPACK for Outdoor Enthusiasts

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Abstract: A multifunctional backpack called MyBACKPACK meets the needs of a modern consumer who prioritizes technological convenience and physical well-being. Incorporating a built-in charger powered by a solar fabric panel addresses the common challenge of maintaining the battery life of electronic devices during daily activities and travel, as they offer opportunities for eco-friendly manufacturing procedures, as well as concerns including increased use of limited resources and potential electronic waste. Furthermore, the essential addition feature of this backpack is the addition of an airbag system, which offers proactive protection and is quickly activated in the event of an accident to reduce the risk of injury or falls, minimizing the impact or damage. In addition, MyBACKPACK coloured with neon bright and including the Global Positioning System (GPS) can assist emergency services in locating and rescuing these climbers, trackers, or hikers, which can benefit in increasing the integration of technology into everyday items, catering to a digitally connected and safety-aware community. MyBACKPACK proves to be an indispensable travel companion for lone travelers venturing into the vast outdoors, thanks to its practical features and life-saving qualities.

Keywords: Hikers people; safety; protection.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adventure tourism allows hikers, trackers, and climbers to seek new or different experiences and grow in popularity, connecting with a new culture or a new landscape and being physically active at the same time. Examples of activities for adventure include day hiking, backpacking, climbing, and others (Head et al., 2017). Next, most hikers, trackers, and climbers, if they want to go climbing or hiking, will bring a backpack to put several important things such as a map, first aid kit, flashlight, navigation, rain jacket, hiking stick, food, water bottle, sunscreen and other (Switchback Travel Staff,2022). In addition, there are some problems they will face when climbing or hiking, such as climbers falling down the gorge, causing injury, collapse, and death while walking or climbing. Mukhtar, A. M. (2024). Furthermore, the next problem is not bringing or

using important things like GPS and touch-light while hiking or climbing. To solve the issues, we created the innovation MyBACKPACK as a solution for the safety of hikers, trackers, and climbers. It is an easy-to-use backpack for hiking or climbing with an airbag we added for safety to the head and body, waterproof materials so easy to carry even in rainy weather, and we added a USB cable on the outside of the bag by using a solar cloth as a substitute for the use of a charger plug.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

2.1 Design and Description of Product

Figure 1. This is a backpack used by hikers, climbers, and trackers without any safety equipment.

Figure 2. This is a backpack with safety equipment including airbag. The backpack before the opening of the airbag.

Figure 3. The airbag will automatically inflate when unexpected changes in movement or location occur, such as landslides or avalanches, and the backpack's airbag will open automatically.

Figure 4. The airbag's colour is neon. Its function is to help emergency services locate and rescue climbers, trackers, or hikers when an accident occurs during the trip. The material of these bags is also waterproof.

Figure 5. My backpack has several features, including solar fabric. Its function is to recharge the gadget through USB charging. These backpacks also have GPS trackers, which can assist emergency services in locating and rescuing these climbers, trackers, or hikers.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Novelty and uniqueness*

MyBACKPACK is safety equipment that includes airbag technology, which can save the lives of hikers, climbers, and trackers, especially those engaged in adventurous activities. These backpacks are created for safety purposes, since the bag's colour is neon bright, and they have GPS, which can assist emergency services in locating and rescuing these climbers, trackers, or hikers. If an incident occurs during an adventurous trip, the airbag will automatically inflate when unexpected changes in movement or location occur, such as landslides or avalanches, and the backpack's airbag will open automatically. The airbag will cushion any injuries or falls, minimizing the impact or damage. These backpacks also cater to tech-savvy explorers by including a simple USB charging option powered by a solar fabric panel and an inbuilt battery, allowing users to easily recharge their electronics and portable lighting when hiking or jungle trekking.

3.2 *Benefit and impact of the innovation*

MyBACKPACK, equipped with charging ports which are supported by the fabric solar, safetyairbags and the Global Positioning System (GPS), embody the increasing integration of technology into everyday items, catering to a digitally connected and safety-aware community. In the context of social function, they improve comfort, usefulness and extra safety equipment during hiking or jungle trekking, illustrating a trend towards integrating personal protection into commonplace items and possibly lowering the risk of accidents. Concerning the environment, they offer opportunities for eco-friendly manufacturing procedures, as well as concerns including increased use of limited resources and potential electronic waste.

3.3 *Commercialization Potential*

As adventure tourism continues to rise in popularity, there is a growing demand for innovative and reliable equipment that enhances safety and convenience for hikers, trackers, and climbers. As of 2022, the global revenue of the outdoor equipment market, of which mountain climbing gear formed a part, reached 23.04 billion U.S. dollars (Topic: Mountain Climbing Worldwide, 2023). Thus, there is a potential for commercialization as the innovation in the combination of safety, durability, and technological integration sets MyBACKPACK apart from conventional backpacks. This unique blend of features positions it as a premium product in the adventure gear market. Besides that, the multi-functionality such as the offering of multiple functionalities in one product, MyBACKPACK can reduce the need for adventurers to carry multiple items, enhancing user experience and satisfaction.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the research show that MyBACKPACK, which integrates GPS, airbag technology, and solar-powered USB-charging, is an important improvement in adventure travel safety equipment. With its many uses, this multipurpose backpack aims to improve traveller's safety and communication, which could reduce accidents and make it easier to search and rescue operations. While the social implications promise improved user experience and safety, the financial effects point

to creating job opportunities and increasing demand for advanced technology. While it presents issues met resource consumption and electrical waste, it also promotes environmentally friendly methods of production. All things considered, MyBACKPACK is an inspiring example of how current technology may be easily integrated into safety equipment for themselves, fulfilling the requirements of being mindful of sustainability and connected through technology society (Fielder & DPT, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION

MyBACKPACK is an innovative safety backpack built exclusively for hikers, climbers, and explorers, with advanced airbag technology that may save lives. Being the first backpack with an integrated airbag system in the world, it expands on its own when the user finds themselves in a hazardous scenario to shield them from impacts brought on by sudden changes in position or movement, like an avalanche or landslide. Furthermore, users can now utilize MyBACKPACK with GPS installed nearby without worrying about getting lost while trekking. Additionally, airbags protect the head, neck, upper body, front, and hips and are highly visible in bright neon colors when the user is in a risky scenario at night. In addition, my backpack satisfies the needs of today's adventurer by offering USB charging via a solar-powered battery, enabling users to replenish their gadgets and lights while they're out and about. MyBACKPACK proves to be an indispensable travel companion for lone travelers venturing into the vast outdoors, thanks to its practical features and life-saving qualities.

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